

INFLUENCE OF STRUCTURAL STITCHING ON COMPOSITE T-JOINT STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Due to their high weight-specific strength and stiffness, fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials are well established in modern lightweight designs. High requirements as increased load capacity, significant weight reduction and high functional integration require a highly integrated design (one-shot-design) with a minimal amount of connection components and fasteners. To connect thin walled carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP)-parts e.g. skins and spars of aircraft flaps or fins, the manufacturing of T-joints containing glass fiber gusset fillers is common practice in aerospace design. However, FRP laminates show poor strength perpendicular to the laminate plane as well as low impact resistance and fracture toughness. Due to bending or tension loading of the part, cracks can form near the gusset filler of the T-joint and can cause debonding between T-web and T-foot. Subsequently, structural failure may occur due to crack growth.

Experimental investigations show that structural stitching can enhance the out-of-plane properties of FRP laminates, although in-plane stiffness and strength can be adversely affected. Objective of the research project HIGHER at Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe (Kaiserslautern, Germany) was the investigation of the potential of structural stitching to improve CFRP T-joints. Different carbon fiber reinforced T-specimen geometries were structurally stitched, infiltrated and cured in a RTM-process. The experiments were carried out using T-specimens in quasi-static tests to obtain the T-pull, -bending and -shear strength of structurally stitched T-joints compared to unstitched references. Different yarn thicknesses (49 and 136 tex) and different yarn materials (glass and aramid) were examined. To investigate the influence of different stitching types, straight stitched and diagonal stitched T-specimens were manufactured and compared to each other. It could be shown that structural stitching can enhance T-pull strength and T-shear strength up to 12 % and 16 %, respectively, and up to 22 % and 14 % for specimens with impact damages.

1 INTRODUCTION

The 3D-reinforcement of composite joints by structural stitching, tufting or Z-pins is a highly effective method for increasing structural properties and damage tolerance. To enhance the performance of composite T-joints made of T-webs and T-flanges, various geometries and types of reinforcement were studied by several authors [1-7]. Cartié et al. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** showed that reinforcement with carbon pins (Z-pins) can delay the crack initiation and increase the maximum T-pull load by approximately 10 %. Also Park et al.

[2] investigated T-joints reinforced with Z-pins under T-pull loading and could observe an increase in ultimate strength by more than 70 %. Furthermore tufted T-joints were investigated; the first failure under T-pull load occurred at a similar load level but the overall load carrying capability of tufted specimens was increased by 100 % **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**]. Tong et al. [7] investigated lap shear failure of stitched specimens and achieved an enhancement of 20 % in strength.

2 TESTS AND EVALUATION METHODS

2.1 Materials and specimen manufacturing

The specifications of the investigated carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics (NCF) are shown in

Table 1. To manufacture the structurally stitched T-joints, the dry laminate preforms were stitched using a modified lock stitch with twisted E-glass- or aramid stitching yarns having a total linear density of 136 tex (glass yarn, tensile strength $R_t = 74.8$ N) or 49 tex (aramid yarn, tensile strength $R_t = 17.4$ N).

NCF specifications			
Number of layers	2		
Fiber orientation (°)	+45/-45	-45/+45	0/90
Area weight (g/m ²)	256	256	257
Pattern	Tricot-Loop		
Carbon fiber type	HTS		
Binding yarn type	PES		
Binding yarn linear yarn density (dtex)	48		

Table 1: Specifications of investigated carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics.

Two different types of carbon fiber preforms were manufactured (see

Figure 2:) in a resin transfer molding process with Saertex® non crimp fabric (NCF) with a HTS fiber and epoxy resin system Hexcel® RTM6. A tri-axial glass fillet was used as gusset filler. The laminate of the T-joint consists of bi-axial plies with a $[(45/-45/0/90)_s]_x$ stacking acc. to

Figure 1 with an area weight acc. to

Table 1.

Figure 1: Stitching directions and stitch positions (left) and T-joint lay up (right) (dimensions in mm).

preform 1

preform 2

Figure 2: Manufactured preforms for T-bending- and T-pull tests (preform 1, left) and T-shear tests (preform 2, right); (dimensions in mm).

The laminate in the T-joint web was approximately 2.18 mm, in the T-joint flange 1.09 mm and the skin 2.90 mm thick. All parts were co-cured. Two different structural stitching configurations were investigated acc. to

Figure 1. The structural stitching seams were applied near the gusset filler for the straight stitched configuration and ran through the gusset filler for the diagonal stitched configuration, both along the entire length of the T-to-skin connection. Introduction of diagonal stitching with a 136 tex glass yarn was not possible due to the high compacted glass fiber gusset filler used, which was difficult to penetrate by the stitching needle. Furthermore the stitching yarn was damaged during stitching through the gusset filler. So an aramid yarn with a lower linear yarn density (49 tex) was chosen for diagonal stitching.

Figure 3 shows the implementation of the diagonal stitching seam by a sewing machine and a computed tomography of the gusset filler area containing a diagonal stitch.

The specimens were cut, after curing according to resin manufacturer specification, with a water-cooled diamond saw (Winter AWS-350-SA/3). Length, width and thickness of the specimens were measured on 12 defined positions and the respective mean values computed.

Pre-tests showed that high forces during T-shear test can cause shear failure in the T-web prior to a shear failure between T-foot and skin. Hence the surface of the web of the T-shear specimens was roughened with sandpaper, cleaned and aluminum cap strips acc. to

Figure 4 were applied using an adhesive (UHU plus endfest 300TM) on the roughened area of the cap strips.

Figure 3: Implementation of diagonal stitching seam (a); diagonal stitched dry preform (b); computed tomography of cured diagonal stitched T-joint (c).

Configuration	Stitching direction	Yarn material	Linear yarn density [tex]	Impact	T-pull test	T-bending test	T-shear test
Type 1	-	-	-		x		x
Type 1 (imp)	-	-	-	x	x	x	x
Type 2	straight	glass	136		x		x
Type 2 (imp)	straight	glass	136	x	x	x	x
Type 3	diagonal	aramid	49		x		x
Type 3 (imp)	diagonal	aramid	49	x	x	x	x
Type 4	straight	aramid	49		x		x
Type 4 (imp)	straight	aramid	49	x		x	

Table 2: Tested non-stitched and structurally stitched T-joint configurations.

Figure 4: T-shear specimen with aluminum cap strips (left) and T-pull specimen (right).

The T-pull specimens were painted white on the front surface to enable the tracking of deformation and crack propagation during test with a charge-coupled device (CCD)-camera. The results of three structurally stitched test configurations with and without impact damage were compared to unstitched references (see Table 2).

2.2 Impact damage methodology

A drop weight tower was used to introduce barely visible impact damages on selected specimens. T-specimens were placed on steel bars (distance 50 mm), fixed with adhesive tape on the lower and upper surface and impacted on the skin side in line with the web of the T-specimen. Pre-tests showed that an impactor with diameter 20 mm and weight 8.7 kg from a drop height of 150 mm caused a barely visible impact (dent depth 2.7 mm) with an applied energy of 12.8 J for the T-pull specimens. The T-bending and T-shear specimens were impacted from a drop height of 110 mm (applied energy of 9.39 J). The impactor was always restrained after first impact with the specimens. Due to the short length of the T-pull specimens (80 mm), delamination near the gusset filler and broken fibers on the lower surface could be detected visually (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Impact test in the drop weight tower (left); delamination and fiber breakage caused by impact (right).

2.3 Types of loading

The T-joints were tested with three different types of quasi-static loads acc. to Table 3 which represent typical load scenarios that can occur in aircraft flaps or fins (e.g. connection between skin and spar) or in stiffened structures under bending load (e.g. structural fairing) under room temperature and dry conditions.

	T-pull	T-bending	T-shear
Number of specimens	52	22	35
Test velocity [mm/min]	2	2	1
Specimen length [mm]	80	280	80
Specimen width [mm]	200	200	100
Testing machine	Schenck Hydropulse (10 kN)	Schenck Hydropulse (40 kN)	PSB250 (250 kN)

Table 3: Test parameters for T-joint tests.

2.3.1 T-pull Tests

The T-pull tests were performed with T-joint specimens cut from preform 1 with a length of 80 mm.

Figure 6 shows a T-pull specimen in the test setup. The specimens were simply supported at the T-foot, clamped and loaded in line of the T-web until debonding between T-web and T-foot or skin and then unloaded. Deformation and crack propagation were recorded optically with a CCD camera (recording frequency 4.5 Hz) and correlated with the applied force.

Figure 6: Front view of T-pull specimen in test setup (left); delamination during test (right).

2.3.2 T-bending Tests

The specimens were cut from preform 1 with a length of 280 mm and were placed in a three point bending test setup with a simple support length of 230 mm acc. to

Figure 7. The specimens were loaded in the midline by means of a loading fin over the specimen width until debonding between T-web and T-foot or skin. All specimens were impacted acc. to 2.2.

Figure 7: T-bending specimen in test setup (left), delamination during test (right).

2.3.3 T-shear Tests

The T-shear specimens were clamped in the test device at the skin and the T-web acc. to Figure 8 and then loaded in line with the T-web in the interface plane between skin and T-foot until detachment of skin and T-foot (see Figure 9). A linear sliding guide ensured that no out-of-plane force was introduced during shear test.

Figure 8: T-shear specimen (top); side view of T-shear specimen in test setup (left) and diagonal front view (right).

Figure 9: Post mortem T-shear specimen; debonded skin (a); debonded T-foot bottom view (b) and top view (c).

3 RESULTS

3.1 T-pull test results

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimens with and without impact damage, with various yarn materials and linear yarn densities during T-pull testing. In both diagrams it can be seen that specimens including straight stitches with glass yarn (Type 2, Type 2 (imp)) failed later compared to non-stitched specimens. They show a significantly increased capability to dissipate energy.

The arithmetic mean values of the normalized forces in Figure 12 show that structural stitching has only a minor influence of the appearance of an initial crack. The maximum T-pull force by contrast could be increased about 12% with straight stitching (Type 2 - glass fiber yarn, 136 tex), but also diagonal stitching and straight stitching with aramid yarn have only minor influences of the maximum force. On the other hand straight stitching with glass yarn has increased the residual load capacity after impact damage about 22%, whereas impacted T-joints containing diagonal stitching with aramid yarn have been adversely affected (decrease of 18%).

Figure 10: Typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimen (without impact damage) during T-pull testing.

Figure 11: Typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimen (with impact damage) during T-pull testing.

Figure 12: Normalized force for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-joints with and without impact damage under T-pull loading.

3.2 T-bending test results

Figure 13 shows typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-joints in T-bending tests. The arithmetic mean values in Figure 14 show that T-bending strength is always been negatively affected by structural stitching. Whereas straight stitching with glass yarn (136 tex) has only a moderate influence, the decrease in the maximum T-bending strength for stitching with the thinner aramid yarn (49 tex) was about 42% for diagonal stitching and 28% for straight stitching.

Figure 13: Typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimen (with impact damage) in T-bending testing.

Figure 14: Normalized force for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-joints with impact damage under T-bending load.

3.3 T-shear test results

Figure 15 and Figure 16 show typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimens with and without impact damage, including various yarn materials and linear yarn densities during T-shear testing. In both diagrams it can be seen that specimens including straight stitches with glass yarn (Type 2, Type 2 (imp)) failed much later than non-stitched specimens. They show a significant increased capability to dissipate energy.

The arithmetic mean values of the normalized forces during T-shear testing (see Figure 17) show that a maximum increase of T-joint shear strength about 6% could be reached due to structural

stitching (straight stitching, glass yarn 136 tex), whereas diagonal and straight stitching with aramid yarn (Type 3, Type 4) show opposite effects (decrease of 9% and 11%). The impacted specimen showed similar behavior. Straight stitching (Type 2 (imp)) has increased the T-shear strength about 14% but diagonal stitching caused a decrease about 7%.

Figure 15: Typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimen (without impact damage) during T-shear testing.

Figure 16: Typical force-time diagrams for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-specimen (with impact damage) during T-shear testing.

Figure 17: Normalized force for non-stitched and structurally stitched T-joints with and without impact damage under T-pull loading.

4 Discussion

Best results in T-strength improvement were achieved by straight stitching with glass yarn (Type 2, Type 2 (imp)). The glass yarn with a linear yarn density of 136 tex increased T-pull- and T-shear strength for specimens without impact damage about 12% and 6% and about 22% and 14% for impacted specimens. Only the T-bending strength was slightly decreased. However, diagonal stitching with aramid yarn (Type 3, 49 tex) showed poor results for all types of T-tests compared to unstitched references. The maximum decrease was measured during T-bending testing with 42%. Also straight stitching with aramid yarn (Type 4) reduced T-strength with a maximum decrease of 28% in T-bending strength. These effects are probably caused by the low linear yarn density and low strength of the aramid yarn. Structural stitching causes always voids (resin pockets) in the laminate due to the misalignment of fiber at stitch area. In case of the stitching with aramid yarn (Type3, Type 4) the influence of the voids may have been much higher than the positive effect of structural stitching in this case. Furthermore, cracks which start near the gusset filler could not be stopped due to diagonal stitching, so straight stitching showed better results in T-strength.

A higher linear yarn density for diagonal stitching in combination with straight stitching may provide better results in T-strength. So the appearance of first cracks could be delayed and crack propagation may be stopped at straight stitches in T-web and T-foot. Precondition for a diagonal stitching with a higher yarn diameter is less compaction of the gusset filler.

5 Conclusions

The introduction of structural stitching opens up the possibility to increase strength of composite T-joints. Experimental studies were carried out to investigate the effect of structural stitching with two different yarn materials and thicknesses and two different stitching types.

The main conclusions of the work are:

- (1) Straight stitching with glass yarn (136 tex) could increase T-pull and T-shear strength up to 12% and 16% (22% and 14% for impacted specimens)
- (2) T-bending strength is always negatively affected by structural stitching
- (3) Diagonal stitching and straight stitching with aramid yarn (49 tex) has detrimental effects on T-strength (maximum decrease of 42% and 28% in T-bending strength)

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